

GRAMMAR TEACHING THROUGH MULTIMEDIA AND DEVELOPMENT OF GRADE 7 ONLINE LANGUAGE SKILLS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 27

Issue 3

Pages: 250-257

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2556

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14006489

Manuscript Accepted: 10-15-2024

Grammar Teaching through Multimedia and Development of Grade 7 Online Language Skills

Lorelei O. Flojo*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to develop multimedia instructional materials in teaching Grammar. In addition, it also aimed to determine the effectiveness of Grammar teaching through multimedia and the development of Grade 7 online language skills in Angono National High School, Angono, Rizal during the school year 2017-2018. It utilized the descriptive and experimental methods of research. The participants were the two sections of Grade 7, Section Loyalty as the experimental group and Section Prudence as the control group who were chosen based on heterogeneous sectioning performance level and first grading performance in English. The developed multimedia instructional materials as validated by the experts were acceptable in terms of multimedia principle, coherence, modality (audibility and visuality) and temporal which helped in the improvement of learners' grammar level. The validity of the developed Edmodo online quiz determined through the results of learners' online performance. It was found out that the experimental group showed a remarkable improvement in Grammar. Based on the findings, the developed multimedia instructional materials in Grammar contributed to improving the learners' speaking skill. It was also confirmed that participants who were exposed to these instructional materials performed better than those participants who did not utilize the activities.

Keywords: *grammar, multimedia, language skills*

Introduction

Teaching grammar is serious and has a lot of challenges that teachers face. One of the problems generally faced by the grade 7 teachers of English is the poor standard of the learners. Learners are even unaware of the basic rules and structural patterns which they are supposed to have learnt at the lower level. They lack confidence in about their own competence in speaking English and lack of adequate and appropriate vocabulary.

In this situation, teaching must begin from the simple grammatical items and proceed towards the complex ones. The biggest problem is that Grade 7 learners find the grammatical lesson so difficult and boring. It needs an instructional material such as multimedia that points out communicative activities which can help classroom interaction more active and learning.

Application of multimedia equipment in the process of grammar teaching can import the real context of teaching resources with simulating, such as integrating sound, images, text, and animation. The multimedia English teaching based on modern education technology is changing the traditional mode of classroom teaching.

The use of multimedia can change the boring and static grammar interesting, which will mobilize the learners' enthusiasm and initiative of learning. When teaching of the sentence structure, teachers can use multimedia to product PPT and explain in detail in this illustrated way. By doing this, it catches learner's interest, explains the Grammar rules, and meets the objectives of the lesson. Besides, the application of multimedia in English grammar teaching enables the learner to create real language context and helps them combine the language form with the meaning well through a lot of collaborative and interactive.

Multimedia instructional materials also save time teaching time as they require to present short time to present large information. They can be used to reveal needs and stimulate learner's question. Thus, learner's interest can be maintained and stimulated to promote their imaginative power. On the whole, multimedia ensures the application of classroom-oriented communication techniques. Therefore, learners should be assisted, encouraged and motivated not only to learn, but also to continue to learn (Demegilio, 2009).

The researcher believed also that with the rapid development of the technology, multimedia instructional materials in the classroom also offered additional possibilities for designing communicative tasks, including the ability to interact in real time with oral and written communication, to conduct information searches to find attractive and meaningful material, and to engage in distance learning.

Moreover, the indications of performance were based on the results of series of evaluation provided the premises of the school like the Division Achievement Test (DAT) and the School Achievement Test (SAT) which focus on the least mastered Grammar lessons. During S.Y. 2016-2017, the result of the Division Achievement in English 7 had a mean score of 17.53 and presently, it has a mean score of 19.92, indicating that English has a low result. Additional to this, during S.Y. 2016-2017, the School Achievement Test in English 7 had a mean score of 30.59, indicating that the mastery level of the learners is 49.32% which is below 50%. They had low performance in Grammar lessons particularly in Content Words like Subject-Verb Agreement, Function Words such as Conjunctions, Pronouns and Antecedents, Determiners, and Structure Words like Phrases. These tests were given not to look into the weaknesses of the instruction rather served as a mirror to develop and achieve quality instructions.

This paper aimed to develop and validate multimedia instructional materials in teaching Grammar because to the best knowledge of

the researcher, no study has been undertaken about Grammar teaching through multimedia and development of Grade 7 online language skills. The researcher believed that multimedia instructional materials are helpful to achieve a better performance. The exposure from multimedia instructional materials introduced the Animated Design on Discussions in Prezi and Powtoon, Audio-video Activities, On-line Quizzes which parents could also sign-in to check the progress of their child and uploaded discussion in You Tube that match different student learning styles and preferences. It also promotes a task-based approach to learning. This will be able to increase students' motivation due to the interactive nature of the activities, allow learners to experience real life and communicatively meaningful language situations and contexts and train learners to self-monitor and self-assess their progress which promotes autonomous learning

Research Questions

This study aimed to develop and validate the multimedia instructional materials in Grammar. In addition, it also aimed to determine the effectiveness of Grammar teaching through multimedia and the development of Grade 7 online language skills in Angono National High School, Angono, Rizal during the school year 2017-2018. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of acceptability of the developed Multimedia Instructional Materials in terms of:
 - 1.1. multimedia principles;
 - 1.2. coherence;
 - 1.3. modality;
 - 1.3.1. audibility;
 - 1.3.2. visuality; and
 - 1.3.3. temporal?
2. what is the level of performance of the experimental and control groups in Grammar as revealed by the pretest and posttest results in terms of;
 - 2.1. content words;
 - 2.1.1. subject-verb-agreement;
 - 2.2. function words;
 - 2.2.1. conjunctions;
 - 2.2.2. determiners;
 - 2.2.3. prepositions;
 - 2.3. structure words;
 - 2.3.1. phrase?
3. Is there a significant difference on the level of performance of the experimental group and control group in Grammar as revealed by the pretest and posttest results in terms of the different lessons?
4. Is there a significant difference on the level of performance of the experimental group and control group in Grammar as revealed by the posttest results in terms of the different lessons?
5. How do the results of the Edmodo Online Quiz validate the developed Multimedia Materials?

Literature Review

In this study, the multimedia instructional materials were described in terms of content that was based on the desired learning competencies of the instructional materials. The combination of various digital media types into an integrated multi-sensory interactive application or presentation to convey a message or information to the learners, in addition to textual information.

Mayer (2009, 2014a), multimedia instruction refers to presenting words and pictures that are intended to foster learning. The words can be in spoken form (such as narration) or in printed form (such as onscreen text). The pictures can be in static form (such as illustrations, diagrams, maps or photos) or dynamic form (such as animation or video). Some common uses of multimedia in e-learning include an animation, video or static graphics with accompanying narration; an animation, video or static graphic with accompanying onscreen text; or a computer-based interactive game, simulation or activity that includes spoken or printed text.

According to the study conducted by Rosales (2015) entitled "Effects of Multimedia Presentation to Reading: A Basis for Developing Reading Remediation Program for Non-Readers in Elvira Razon Aranilla Elementary School S.Y. 2015-1016," she concluded that multimedia presentations allow the comparative visions of the same learning materials. It offers exciting possibilities for meeting the needs of 21st century learners. Learners become more attentive when they saw new like widescreen and the different multimedia presentation. Multimedia presentations are enhanced when the structures for organizing the information are activated.

Likewise, in the research conducted by Shah et. Al., (2015) entitled "Impact of Multimedia-aided Teaching on Students' Academic Achievement and Attitude at Elementary Level!" they concluded that MAT has changed the teaching and learning process. The lessons presented in this way are more effective and better comprehended.

Moreso, Sorden (2015) said that multimedia today refers not only to what is presented to computers, but also through the composition of text and illustrations in print media.

From the book of Bilbao et. al (2006), technologies as link to new knowledge, resources and high order thinking skill have entered classrooms and schools worldwide. Personal computers, CD-ROMS, online services, the World Wide Web and other innovative technologies have enriched curricula and altered the type of teaching available in the classroom. School's access to the technology is increasing steadily every day and most of these new technologies are now even used in the traditional classrooms. With the diversity of learners, breakthroughs in technology and multiple teacher perspectives, an innovative teaching is one of the answers to the global demands for quality education.

Methodology

Research Design

In accomplishing this study which attempted to develop and validate multimedia instructional materials in teaching Grammar, an experimental method of research was utilized. Experimental design was appropriate in this study for which the level of performance of the two groups of participants were determined, compared and analyzed by the differences revealed in their pretest and posttest. Mottola (2009) defined experimental design as a planned interference in the natural order of events by the researcher. He does something more than carefully observing what is occurring. This emphasis on experiment reflects the higher regard generally given to information so derived.

This study also used the descriptive-survey method of research to attain the main aim of this study. Ariola (2006), mentioned that the descriptive research maybe defined as a purposive process of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about the prevailing data of the conditions, situations, practices, beliefs, processes, trends, developments as well as cause-effect relationship and then making adequate interpretation about such data with or without statistical method.

Respondents

The present study used two (2) sections from the grade seven learners of Angono National High School who were taking up the K to 12 Curriculum. Sixty-Eight learners from the two sections with equal variable were selected. These were the experimental group who were exposed to the multimedia instructional materials in teaching Grammar and the control group who were not exposed to it and taught using the traditional way of teaching during second grading period.

For the acceptability of the researcher-made questionnaire checklist, a month before second grading period, the researcher asked and gave the developed multimedia instructional materials to the English teacher participants of Vivencio Memorial National High School and Regional Lead School for the Arts and to the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) specialists of Angono National High School to examine the developed materials following the given scale.

Instrument

In this study, the sources of data were the standardized division achievement test and the researcher-made questionnaire checklist.

The periodical test in different lessons such as Subject-Verb Agreement, was composed of twenty-one (21) items, Conjunctions with thirteen (13) items, Pronoun and Antecedent with nine (9) items, Determiners with thirteen (13) items also and Phrases with four (4) items as prescribed by the division's target competency in Grammar for second quarter.

Another one was the researcher-made questionnaire checklist used in evaluating the developed multimedia instructional materials. It contained the criteria of evaluating several aspects such as Multimedia Principle, Coherence Principle Modality Principle (visuality and audibility) and Temporal Principle.

Procedure

The researcher made an assessment using the Division Achievement Test and School Achievement test regarding the academic performance of Grade 7 learners. The researcher came up with a discernment to the development and validation of multimedia instructional materials used in the teaching process that focused on Grammar lessons for it had been the problem of the learners why they did not cooperate with their individual performance task and show confidence to speak nor answer the question of their teacher in English. With this, the researcher evaluated the use of the developed multimedia instructional materials for Grade 7 learners used in different lessons such as Subject-Verb Agreement, Conjunctions, Pronoun-Antecedent, Determiners, and Phrases.

The researcher prepared the multimedia instructional materials for the experimental group. Gathering of the necessary data and information regarding the related literatures and studies followed. Analyzing and studying the collected data which were useful to the present study were done.

The researcher also asked permission from their English Department Chairman and the School Principal to conduct this study in the school and to use the learners for accomplishing this experimental study. Before the implementation of the multimedia instructional materials in Grammar to the participants, the pretest and posttest were constructed which were based on the objectives of the Kto12 content standard of learning course outline in English.

The researcher constructed an instrument used in administering the study. Upon the approval of the authorities, the researcher prepared

a 60-item Multiple Choice test which underwent statistical treatment. The pretest and posttest were based on the topics in Grammar with least mastered skills. The developed multimedia instructional materials in Grammar were used by the experimental group right after their pretest. For the acceptability of the researcher-made questionnaire checklist, a month before administering the developed instructional materials to the experimental group, the researcher asked and gave the developed multimedia instructional materials to the English teacher respondents from other schools for further study and suggestion. She also asked the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) specialists of Angono National High School to examine the developed materials. Data were analyzed, interpreted and treated with a proper statistical treatment.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Level of Acceptability of the Developed Multimedia Instructional Materials in Grammar with Respect to Multimedia Principle, Coherence, Modality (Audibility and Visuality) and Temporal

Table 1. Mean Results on the Level of Acceptability of the Developed Multimedia Instructional Materials as Evaluated by English Teachers and Information and Communication Technology Specialists with Respect to Multimedia Principle

<i>Multimedia Principle</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
<i>The developed Multimedia Instructional Materials...</i>			
1.	Words and graphics illustrations are more conducive to learning, rather than just text or graphics alone.	4.86	Very Much Accepted
2.	Graphics, animation, or video that are relevant to the words on the presentation	4.86	Very Much Accepted
3.	Representational graphics portray a single element such as a photo along with a caption explaining it.	4.86	Very Much Accepted
4.	Graphics and texts which enable to answer questions about the processes involved.	4.57	Very Much Accepted
5.	The video and animated design presentation are balanced and related and not confusing to the learners learning process.	4.71	Very Much Accepted
Overall		4.77	Very Much Accepted

It can be deduced from the table that the English teachers and Information and Communications Technology (ICT) specialists evaluated the Multimedia Principle of the developed multimedia instructional materials in Grammar as Very Much Accepted with the obtained mean of 4.77.

This means that the developed instructional materials provide lessons and activities that suit the needs of the students and one of the classroom instructions needed by the teachers in teaching Grammar.

This study is parallel to the study of Mayer (2009), the rationale for multimedia instruction is that people learn better from words and pictures than from words alone, which can be called the multimedia principle.

Table 2. Mean Results on the Level of Acceptability of the Developed Multimedia Instructional Materials as Evaluated by English Teachers and Information and Communication Technology Specialists with Respect to Coherence

<i>Coherence</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
<i>The developed Multimedia Instructional Materials...</i>			
1.	The multimedia presentations do not contain extraneous sound.	4.57	Very Much Accepted
2.	The image placed in each topic complements learner's thinking processes.	4.57	Very Much Accepted
3.	Sounds and graphics presented stimulate student's interest which match with the instructional goal while at the same time promote learner's interest.	4.71	Very Much Accepted
4.	The multimedia presentations used related background content and relevant graphics onscreen.	4.71	Very Much Accepted
5.	Simple, basic and concise on-screen text helps the learning process.	4.86	Very Much Accepted
Overall		4.69	Very Much Accepted

It is revealed in the table that the English teachers and Information and Communications Technology (ICT) specialists evaluated Coherence of the Developed Multimedia Instructional Materials as Very Much Accepted with a mean average of 4.69.

This implies that the researcher found out that Multimedia Instructional Materials in Grammar are very clear and easy to understand. Simple, basic and concise on-screen text helps the learning process which matches with the instructional goal.

The result supports the study of Doolittle (2009), multimedia presentations should focus on clear and concise presentations. Presentations that add "bells and whistles" or extraneous information (e.g. to increase interest) impede student learning.

The table 3 shows that the developed Multimedia Instructional Materials were Very Much Accepted as evaluated by the English teachers and Information and Communications Technology (ICT) specialists with respect to Modality (Audibility and Visuality).

This is supported by the average mean score of 4.71. This implies that animated images and auditory text when combined in the presentations stimulated the interest of the students. It is important to consider in every topic the verbal and visual style suited to the

mental ability of the students in their learning process.

Table 3. Mean Results on the Level of Acceptability of the Developed Multimedia Instructional Materials as Evaluated by English Teachers and Information and Communication Technology Specialists with Respect to Modality (Audibility and Visuality)

Modality (Audibility and Visuality)		Mean	VI
<i>The developed Multimedia Instructional Materials...</i>			
1.	The words are presented as auditory narration.	4.67	Very Much Accepted
2.	The presentation material was a mixture of the auditory and visual modalities.	4.57	Very Much Accepted
3.	Animated images are processed in the visual model and does not overlap with the auditory text.	4.71	Very Much Accepted
4.	Effectively combined the visual channel for graphical material and the verbal channel for the explanation.	4.71	Very Much Accepted
5.	Execution of the verbal and visual style in every topic is in the level of students.	4.83	Very Much Accepted
Overall		4.71	Very Much Accepted

The findings support the study of Sorden (2012), this principle relates directly to the theory of Dual Coding which suggests that we have two types of working memory, one verbal and one visual, and that we learn best when both channels are used together, rather than overlooking one or the other.

Table 4. Mean Results on the Level of Acceptability of the Developed Multimedia Instructional Materials as Evaluated by English Teachers and Information and Communication Technology Specialists with Respect to Temporal

Temporal		Mean	VI
<i>The developed Multimedia Instructional Materials...</i>			
1.	The words are spoken at the same time they are illustrated in the animation.	4.86	Very Much Accepted
2.	Multimedia builds mental connections between verbal and visual representations to the learners.	4.71	Very Much Accepted
3.	Multimedia maintains connections to the learners if the time between hearing a sentence and seeing the corresponding portion of animation is short.	4.86	Very Much Accepted
4.	Designed not only to present information but it helps learners build connections between corresponding words and graphics.	4.71	Very Much Accepted
5.	Presents corresponding words and pictures simultaneously rather than successively.	4.71	Very Much Accepted
Overall		4.77	Very Much Accepted

It can be noticed from the table that English Teachers and Information and Communications Technology (ICT) specialists evaluated the developed Multimedia Instructional Materials in Grammar as Very Much Accepted in terms of Temporal Principle as supported by the obtained mean of 4.77.

The result implies that in searching for a solution in understanding the Grammar lessons, the multimedia instructional materials presentations with corresponding words and graphics help the learners to build connection and understand the lesson. It helps the learners better understand explanation when texts and pictures are presented at the same time.

This pattern of results, also consistent with a meta-analysis by Balasta (2010), supports the temporal continuity principle: People learn better from multimedia lessons when narration.

Level of Performance of the Experimental and Control Groups in Grammar as Revealed by the Pretest and Posttest Results in Terms of the Different Lessons

Table 5. Level of Performance of the Experimental and Control Groups in Grammar as Revealed by the Pretest and Posttest Results in Terms of the Different Lessons

Lessons	Experimental						Control					
	Pretest			Posttest			Pretest			Posttest		
	Mean	Sd.	VI	Mean	Sd.	VI	Mean	Sd.	VI	Mean	Sd.	VI
S-V-A	8.76	3.19	S	13.00	3.25	VS	7.06	3.52	FS	7.32	2.77	FS
Conjunctions	5.76	2.66	S	10.18	1.78	VS	4.91	2.84	FS	5.74	2.12	S
Pronoun and Antecedent	3.65	1.65	S	6.44	1.31	VS	3.00	1.48	FS	3.62	1.83	S
Determiners	6.38	2.85	S	10.50	3.00	O	5.56	2.87	S	5.65	3.02	S
Phrases	1.03	.63	FS	3.47	.83	O	1.00	.78	P	1.26	1.26	FS

The findings imply that the learners in the control and experimental groups have increased their performance using the traditional method and the multimedia instructional materials. The posttest shows a better performance in using the multimedia instructional materials perhaps it provided instructional effectiveness that gave a multisensory experience to the learners.

The present study is congruent with the findings of Dotimas (2012) which found out that there is an increase on the performance in the posttest after exposure using his developed instructional materials.

The Significant Difference on the Level of Performance of the Experimental Group and Control Group in Grammar as Revealed by the Pretest and Posttest in Terms of the Different Lessons

Table 6. *Significant Difference on the Level of Performance of the Experimental Group in Grammar as Revealed by the Pretest and Posttest in Terms of the Different Lessons*

<i>Lessons</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd.</i>	<i>Mean Diff.</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>HO</i>	<i>VI</i>
Subject-Verb-Agreement	Pretest	8.76	3.19	4.235	6.016	33	.000	R	S
	Posttest	13.00	3.25						
Conjunctions	Pretest	5.76	2.66	4.412	9.697	33	.000	R	S
	Posttest	10.18	1.78						
Pronoun and Antecedent	Pretest	3.65	1.65	2.794	7.653	33	.000	R	S
	Posttest	6.44	1.31						
Determiners	Pretest	6.38	2.85	4.118	5.831	33	.000	R	S
	Posttest	10.50	3.00						
Phrases	Pretest	1.03	.63	2.441	13.945	33	.000	R	S
	Posttest	3.47	.83						
Total	Pretest	25.59	8.45	18.000	11.834	33	.000	R	S
	Posttest	43.59	6.27						

It can be seen from the table that there exists significant difference on the level of performance of the experimental group in the pretest and posttest with respect to the different lessons since the computed p-value are all less than .05 level of significance, hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

The findings imply that the use of instructional materials enhance learners' level of performance in Content, Function and Structure Words. It increases learners' motivation, which leads to the feeling of personal empowerment and sense of achievement.

This result conforms with the study of Jimenez (2008) according to her study, "Effectiveness of Module in Teaching Integers" revealed that the performance of the experimental group in the posttest was significantly better than the performance in the pretest and that the learning through the modular instruction took place.

Table 7. *Significant Difference on the Level of Performance of the Control Group in Grammar as Revealed by the Pretest and Posttest in Terms of the Different Lessons*

<i>Lessons</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd.</i>	<i>Mean Diff.</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>HO</i>	<i>VI</i>
Subject-Verb-Agreement	Pretest	7.06	3.52	.265	.458	33	.650	FR	NS
	Posttest	7.32	2.77						
Conjunctions	Pretest	4.91	2.84	.824	2.245	33	.032	R	S
	Posttest	5.74	2.12						
Pronoun and Antecedent	Pretest	3.00	1.48	.618	1.635	33	.111	FR	NS
	Posttest	3.62	1.8.						
Determiners	Pretest	5.56	2.87	.088	.168	33	.867	FR	NS
	Posttest	5.65	3.02						
Phrases	Pretest	1.00	.78	.265	.942	33	.353	FR	NS
	Posttest	1.26	1.26						
Total	Pretest	21.53	7.88	2.059	1.648	33	.109	FR	NS
	Posttest	23.59	8.67						

It implies that the learner exposed to the multimedia instructional acquired knowledge and skills due to percentage increases of their scores in the posttest.

This is similarly manifested in the findings of San Antonio (2007), in utilizing the pretest and posttest on her study, she found out that the performance of the two groups in the pretest and posttest differ significantly in the different learning areas.

Significant Difference on the Level of Performance of the Experimental Group and Control Group in Grammar as Revealed by the Posttest Results in Terms of the Different Lessons

The results further imply that the level of performance of the experimental group is better than the control group perhaps due the multimedia instructional materials that enhanced the learners to be more motivated and cooperative in the different illustrations presented.

The findings are in affirmation with the study of Patero (2008), also found out that his developed and validated computer-based lecture on problem solving in mathematics is an effective instructional material in assisting the teacher and the learners in the teaching-learning process.

It revealed that the computer-based lecture developed by the researcher was significantly effective in learning different topics in Mathematics to the learners.

Table 8. Significant Difference on the Level of Performance of the Experimental Group and Control Group in Grammar as Revealed by the Posttest Results in Terms of the Different Lessons

Lessons	Group	Mean	Sd.	Mean Diff.	T	Df	Sig.	HO	VI
Subject-Verb-Agreement	Experimental	13.00	3.25	5.676	7.753	66	.000	R	S
	Control	7.32	2.77						
Conjunctions	Experimental	10.18	1.78	4.441	9.342	66	.000	R	S
	Control	5.74	2.12						
Pronoun and Antecedent	Experimental	6.44	1.31	2.824	7.332	66	.000	R	S
	Control	3.62	1.83						
Determiners	Experimental	10.50	3.00	4.853	6.646	66	.000	R	S
	Control	5.65	3.02						
Phrases	Experimental	3.47	.83	2.206	8.527	66	.000	R	S
	Control	1.26	1.26						
Total	Experimental	43.59	6.27	20.000	10.904	66	.000	R	S
	Control	23.59	8.67						

Validation Results of the Developed Multimedia Instructional Materials in Grammar Using Edmodo Online Quiz

Table 9. Validation Results of the Developed Multimedia Instructional Materials in Grammar Using Edmodo Online Quiz

It indicates the computed mean graphical presentation on the level of validity of the developed multimedia instructional materials in Grammar. It illustrates the performance of the experimental group in the Edmodo online quiz with respect to the different topics.

The results further imply that the level of performance of the experimental group increased perhaps due the multimedia instructional materials that enhanced them to be more motivated and cooperative. The Edmodo Online Quiz helped the teachers in facilitating the development of academic speaking and writing skills of the learners. It also helped the learners to have an opportunity to monitor, improved and attained their target performance in Grammar.

This is parallel to the study of Manalo (2016) entitled “Multimedia: A Technique in Teaching process in the classrooms,” it was revealed that through the interaction with multimedia, the learners become increasingly familiar with academic vocabulary and language structure. Both studies used multimedia that provides the students to gather information and develop greater confidence in their ability to use English because they need to interact with the online through reading, writing as well as speaking.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

The developed multimedia instructional materials in grammar has proven accepted by the respondents based on their standards in instructional material preparation.

The utilization of the developed multimedia instructional materials in grammar significantly contribute to the enhancement of the academic performance of the target learners.

The developed multimedia instructional materials in grammar provided academic aid both to teachers and students in facilitating teaching-learning process in grammar.

References

- Balasta, J. (2010). Development and Validation of Manipulative Activities in Teaching Social Skills among Children with Autism “Unpublished Undergraduate Thesis University of Rizal System, Morong, Rizal
- Bilbao, P.B. Corpuz, B. B. et. al. (2012) The Teaching profession (2nd Edition). 776 Aurora Blvd., Corner Boston St., Cubao Quezon City, Metro Manila: Lorimar Publishing, Incorporated.
- Demegilio, V. (2009). Development, Validation and Acceptability of Computer-Aid Instructional Materials of Selected Topics in Elementary Algebra.
- Doolittle, P. E. (2009). ML: Empirical Results and practical Applications. Virginia Technology. Retrieved from <http://eduscapes.com/instruction/articles/multimediaLearningEmpericalResults.pdf>.
- Dotimas, L. (2012). “Development, Validation and Acceptability of Modules in Ecology for College Students.” Unpublished Master’s Thesis, URS Rodriguez.
- Jimenez, J. (2008). “Development and Validation of Interactive Activities in Selected Reading Skills”, “Unpublished Master’s Thesis University of Rizal System, Morong, Rizal.
- Manalo, J. (2016). “Integrating Mayer’s Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning in Designing Instruction for Science Among Grade III Pupils as Perceived by the Teachers of Lucena East District, SY 2016-2017”, Unpublished Thesis, Manuel S. Enverga University Foundation, Lucena City, Quezon Province.
- Mayer R. E. (2009). Multimedia learning (2nd Edition). New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Mottola, R.M., (2009), “The Basics of Experimental Design”. Retrieved from <http://liutaiomottola.com/myth/exodesig.html>.2009.
- Petero, N. (2008). “Development and Evaluation of Computer-Based Lectures on Problem Solving in Mathematics.” Luzon Science Consortium, Vol. 3 No. 2.
- Rosales, C.R. (2015). “Effects of Multimedia presentation to Reading: A Basis for Developing Reading Remediation Program for Non-Readers in Elvira Razon Aranilla Elementary School, S.Y. 2015-2016.”, Unpublished Thesis, Manuel S. Enverga University Foundation, Lucena City, Quezon Province.
- San Antonio Eleanor P. (2007). “Development and Validation of Worktext in Physics 2. For College Students “Unpublished Master’s Thesis, University of Rizal System.
- Shah, I & Khan, M. (2015). Impact of Multimedia-aided Teaching on Student’s Academic Achievement and Attitude at Elementary Level. Islamad, Pakistan. US-China. Education Review A, May 2015, Vol. 5, No. 5 349-360 doi:10.17265/2161623x/2015.05.006.
- Sorden, S.D. (2015). A Cognitive Approach to Instructional Design for Multimedia Learning. Informing Science Journal. Retrieved from <http://www.cwejournal.org/pdf/vol17no1/CWEVO7NO1P33-36.pdf>.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Lorelei O. Flojo

Dr. Vivencio B. Villamayor Integrated School
Department of Education – Philippines